

GENERATING 8 MW OF ELECTRICITY FROM A MUNICIPAL SOLID WASTE (MSW) INCINERATOR

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ABSTRACT

This research work was carried out at the Oshodi Solid Waste Incineration Station in Lagos, Nigeria to determine the feasibility of generating 8 MW of electricity from the incineration plant that has remained dormant for over 20 years. The plant is equipped with a water wall boiler, turbine, feed heaters, scrubber and other auxiliaries. It has facilities to process up to 220 metric tons of solid waste continuously on a daily basis with a throughput capacity of 9.2 tons/hour. The average moisture content of waste in Lagos state is estimated to be 35% with an average calorific value of 9000 kJ/Kg. The hourly rate of heat released in the moving grate combustor was calculated to be 82,800 MJ/Kg hence the heat supplied in the boiler per unit mass flow rate is estimated to be 2716.86 kW per kg/s with a boiler steam flow rate of 7.73 kg/s. The specific steam consumption was found to be 3.49 kg/kWh with a power output per unit mass flow rate of 7.73 kW per kg/s.

KEYWORDS: solid waste, incinerator, calorific value, steam, power, electricity.

Received for Publication: 03/09/13

Accepted for Publication: 21/11/13

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Nomenclature

E = energy recovery potential (kJ)

E_{eq} = equivalent energy recovery potential (kWh)

h = Enthalpy of steam (kJ/kg)

MSW = municipal solid waste

MW = Mega Watt

m_s = boiler steam flow rate (kg/s)

η_{th} = thermal efficiency of plant

P = power generating potential

Q = Heat supplied by the boiler per unit mass flow rate (KW per kg/s)

W = power output per unit mass flow rate (KW per kg/s)

INTRODUCTION

Solid waste management system provides a means by which solid waste generated from the municipal area (residential homes, business centres, public institutions etc) can be disposed of effectively. Once re-use and recycling have been maximized, there still remains a large fraction of municipal wastes which must be disposed of in the best manner possible. The vast majority of the remaining waste should be sent to waste-to-energy incinerators in order to recover energy and limit pollutants, and only that portion of waste which can neither be reused/recycled nor incinerated should be sent to landfills (Meisen, 2010).

Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) contains organic as well as inorganic matter, the latent energy present in its organic fraction can be recovered for gainful utilization through adoption of suitable waste processing and treatment technologies. In recent years, much emphasis has been placed on sustainable MSW management, and the incineration of waste with energy recovery is one of the interesting options. A large portion of the waste has significant energy potential which should be utilized and the development of Energy from Waste plants in the

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major cities could provide an effective and permanent solution to the waste problem facing major cities at the current time (Amin, 2011).

Lagos State is a metropolitan city that is emerging into a mega city in Nigeria with a very large population of about 11 million people (according to the 2005 Federal Office of Statistics estimate) and generate in excess of 10 thousand metric tons of solid waste on a daily basis. This necessitates the need to establish an effective waste management system. In view of this an incineration plant was built not only to address the problem of waste management but also to provide electricity because of the frequent power failure experience in most part of the state.

An incineration plant can combust large quantities of MSW, the object of this thermal treatment method is the reduction of the volume of the treated waste with simultaneous utilization of the energy content. The heat produced by an incinerator can be used to generate steam which in turn may be used to drive a turbine in order to produce electricity and also probably provide district heating as it is done in some countries like Denmark and Sweden.

In general, 100 tons of raw MSW with 50-60% organic matter can generate about 1- 1.5 Mega Watt power, depending upon the waste characteristics, this is enough to power up more than 2000 households in a power intensive district and 5000 households in less power-hungry district respectively for 24 hours (Kerry, 2012). This study will undertake the feasibility of producing 8 MW of electricity from the combustion of a specific quantity of MSW in a field erected incineration plant.

METHODOLOGY

This study was carried out at the Lagos state waste incineration plant and data collection was obtained from the plant, Lagos State Waste Management Authority (LAWMA), as well as from the waste transfer station in Oshodi.

Prior to the installation of an incineration plant, the collection of MSW must be optimized to ensure there is no interruption of continuous daily operation of the plant. According to the data provided by LAWMA, about 10.6 million metric tons of waste was generated in 2008 in Lagos state which translated to about 29,000 metric tons of waste per day. The waste generated from Epe LGA alone was about 530 metric tons per day which is enough to supply the daily throughput requirement of the plant. The waste generated from all the local government of Lagos state is shown in Table 1.

The composition of waste varies from city to city and so is the average calorific value of the waste. However, using the waste composition survey of Lagos state shown in Fig. 1, the average calorific value of the waste characterization is given as 9 MJ/kg (Oyelola et al., 2011).

ASSESSMENT OF POTENTIAL ENERGY OF MSW

A rough assessment of energy recovery potential from MSW through different treatment methods can be made from knowledge of its calorific value and organic fraction. In thermo-chemical conversion such as incineration, all of the organic matter, biodegradable as well as non-biodegradable, contributes to the energy output.

The energy recovery potential E (kJ/day)

The energy recovery potential for the waste characterization is obtained from equ. (1)

$$E = m * CV \text{ ----- Equ. (1)}$$

Where m = mass of waste to be incinerated per day

CV = Average calorific value of the waste

The equivalent energy recovery potential in kWh

$$E_{eq} = \frac{E}{3600} \text{ kWh ----- Equ. (2)}$$

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Power generation potential

$$P = \frac{E_{eq}}{24} \text{ kW} \text{ -----Equ. (3)}$$

Net power generation potential

$$P = \frac{E_{eq} * \eta_{th}}{24} \text{ kW} \text{ -----Equ. (4)}$$

i.e.

$$P = \frac{m * CV * \eta_{th}}{24 * 3600} \text{ kW} \text{ ---Equ. (4)}$$

Where η_{th} = Thermal efficiency for a conventional plant

Given that $m = 220,000\text{kg}$, $CV = 9,000\text{kJ/Kg}$ and $\eta_{th} = 0.35$ (for conventional thermal power plant). Hence applying equ. (4)

$$P = \frac{m * CV * \eta_{th}}{24 * 3600} \text{ Kw}$$

$$P = \frac{220000 * 9000 * 0.35}{24 * 3600}$$

$$P = 8020.8\text{kW}$$

The plant layout of the 8 MW facility is represented in fig. (2) and the thermodynamic Cycle showing the flow of fluid within the components is represented in Fig. (3).

The enthalpies of the steam at various points in the cycle were calculated by interpolation using the steam property table and presented in table 2 and also the enthalpies of the condensate through the feed heaters at various point in the cycle is presented in table 3. $h_{13-17} = h_f$ at 5°C less than the saturation temperature of the preceding bled steam pressure

The application of the steady state energy equation to the open feed heaters was done in order to calculate the mass flow rate of the bled steam (y_1, y_2, y_3, y_4 and y_5).

Steam at a pressure of 80 bar is bled into the feed heater 1 having enthalpy $h_{f1} = 1317.1 \text{ kJ/kg}$. (see fig. 4).

Applying the steady state energy equation to the feed heater 1

$$[\sum_{in} y h - \sum_{out} y h] = 0 \text{ ---- Equ. (5)}$$

i.e

$$\sum_{in} y h = \sum_{out} y h$$

$$y_1 h_2 + (1 - y_1) h_{16} = y_1 h_{f1} + (1 - y_1) h_{17}$$

$$y_1 h_2 + h_{16} - y_1 h_{16} = y_1 h_{f1} + h_{17} - y_1 h_{17}$$

$$y_1 (h_2 - h_{16}) + h_{16} = y_1 (h_{f1} - h_{17}) + h_{17}$$

$$y_1 (h_2 - h_{16} - h_{f1} + h_{17}) = h_{17} - h_{16}$$

$$y_1 = \frac{h_{17} - h_{16}}{h_2 - h_{16} - h_{f1} + h_{17}}$$

$$y_1 = \frac{222.5}{2227.5} \text{ ---Equ. (6)}$$

$$y_1 = \frac{222.5}{2227.5} = 0.1 \text{ kg/s}$$

Similar analysis and calculations were done for the other feed heaters and the results tabulated in Table 4.

Power Output per Unit Mass Flow rate from the Boiler (kW per kg/s steam flow)

$$W = (h_1 - h_2) + (h_2 - h_3)(1 - y_1) + (h_3 - h_4)(1 - y_1 - y_2) + (h_5 - h_6)(1 - y_1 - y_2) + (h_6 - h_7)(1 - y_1 - y_2 - y_3) + (h_8 - h_9)(1 - y_1 - y_2 - y_3 - y_4) + (h_9 - h_{10})(1 - y_1 - y_2 - y_3 - y_4 - y_5) \text{ ----Equ. (7)}$$

$$= (3485.7 - 3322.5) + (3322.5 - 3177.3)(1 - 0.1) + (3377.3 - 3046.2)(1 - 0.1 - 0.0655) + (3667.9 - 3667.9)(1 - 0.1 - 0.0655) + (3667.9 - 3224.9)(1 - 0.1 - 0.0655 - 0.029) + (3051.6 - 2741.1)(1 - 0.1 - 0.0655 - 0.029 - 0.097) + (2741.1 - 2659.8)(1 - 0.1 - 0.0655 - 0.029 - 0.097 - 0.032)$$

$$= 1035.12 \text{ kW per kg/s}$$

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The required steam flow from the boiler to give a power generated of 8 MW:

$$\text{Boiler Steam Flow Rate (kg/s)} \quad m = \frac{\text{Power generated}}{\text{Power Output per Unit Mass Flowrate from the Boiler}} \text{ Equ. (8)}$$

$$m = \frac{8,000}{1035.12}$$

$$= 7.73 \text{ kg/s}$$

The Specific Steam Consumption

$$S.S.C = \frac{3600}{\text{Power Output per Unit Mass Flowrate from the Boiler}} \text{ kg/kWh} \text{ --- Equ. (9)}$$

$$= \frac{3600}{1035.12} \text{ kg/kWh}$$

$$= 3.49 \text{ kg/kWh}$$

The Heat Supplied in the Boiler per Unit Mass Flowrate (kW per kg/s)

$$Q = (h_1 - h_{17}) + (h_5 - h_4) * (1 - y_1 - y_2) \text{ --- Equ. (10)}$$

$$= (3485.7 - 1287.7) + (3667.9 - 3046.2)(1 - 0.1 - 0.0655)$$

$$= 2716.86 \text{ kW per kg/s}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The study shows that 82,800 MJ/Kg of heat can be released per hour from the incineration of 9.2 tons of MSW on a continuous duty basis which can produce 2716.86 kW per kg/s of heat per unit mass flow rate in the boiler having a boiler steam flow rate of 7.73kg/s and developing 1035.12 kW per kg/s of power in the turbine.

Today there is a concerted focus on optimizing plants' production of electricity in order to achieve more efficient energy production. The boiler steam flow rate was determined because it could be used to estimate one of the characteristics of the plant vis-a-viz the overall efficiency of the plant.

MSW is a domestic energy resource with the potential to provide a significant amount of energy. The 8 MW of electricity generated by the incineration plant can be used to power up to 30,000 residential homes of two bedroom flats and this will reduce significantly the overwhelming demand on the use of fossil fuel to fire our thermal power plants.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study shows that incineration in addition to being a waste management option could be considered as a complement to conventional power production and could play an appreciable role for electricity generation in a state where power supply is not stable.

Furthermore this study provides an overall picture of the energy recovery potentials of the Oshodi incineration plant and could provide valuable information that can support a decision-making process for the resuscitation of the plant.

REFERENCES

- Amin K. (2011):** Energy Potential from Municipal Solid Waste in Tanjung Langsat Landfill, Johor, Malaysia, *International Journal of Engineering Science and Technology (IJEST)*, Vol. 3, No.12, pp. 8560- 8568.
- Kalu C. and Modugu W. (2009):** Evaluation of Solid Waste Management Policy in Benin Metropolis, Edo State, Nigeria, *African Scientist*, Vol. 10, No. 1, pp. 1-6.
- Kerry J. (2012):** Clean Earth Technology; Waste – The Next Commodity. www.cleaneartshsb.com. Accessed June 23rd, 2012.

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Morris M. (1998): Electricity Production from Solid Waste Fuels Using advanced Gasification Technologies, www.tps.se. Accessed May 3rd, 2012.

Meisen P. (2010): Waste-to-Energy Plants. www.geni.org . Accessed feb.20th, 2013.

Oyelola, O. Babatunde, A. and Abiodun, A. (2011): Appraisal of Municipal Solid Waste Management in Lagos Metropolis, *Continental Journal*, Vol. 2, No. 2, pp. 48-54.

Rajput R.K. (2009): Thermal Engineering, 7th edition, Laxmi Publication limited, New Delhi.

Skortzki Y.A. and Vopat W.A. (1990): Power Station Engineering and Economy, 2nd edition, Edward Arnold Publishing Company, London.

Table 1: The Estimated Solid Waste Generation in Lagos State.

S/N	LOCAL GOVT. AREA	ESTIMATED ANNUAL WASTE GENERATION (TONES)		
		2006	2007	2008
1	Agege	662,880	715,910	773,180
2	Badagry	190,690	205,950	222,420
3	Epe	163,490	176,530	190,650
4	Eti- Osa	245,170	264,790	285,970
5	Ibeju – Lekki	39,590	43,550	48,780
6	Ikeja	326,900	353,050	381,290
7	Ikorodu	290,580	313,820	338,930
8	Lagos Island	263,330	284,400	307,150
9	Lagos Mainland	435,870	470,730	503,390
10	Mushin	853,570	921,850	995,600
11	Ojo	345,060	372,660	402,480
12	Shomolu	572,070	617,840	667,270
13	Alimosho	681,040	716,080	773,370
14	Oshodi- Isolo	717,360	774,750	836,730
15	Surulere	735,520	794,360	857,910
16	Ajeromi- Ifelodun	940,870	1,019,920	1,101,520
17	Amuwo Odofin	354,140	382,470	413,070
18	Apapa	245,170	264,790	285,970
19	Ifako Ijaiye	372,300	402,090	434,250
20	Kosofe	653,800	706,100	762,590
		9,089,400	9,801,640	10,582,520

Table 2: The enthalpies of steam from point 1-10

Point	Pressure (bar)	Temperature (°C)	Enthalpy (kJ/Kg)
1	140	560	3485.7
2	80	480	3322.5
3	40	385	3177.3
4	20	310	3046.2
5	20	590	3667.9
6	20	590	3667.9
7	8	380	3225.0
8	2	290	3051.6
9	0.5	130	2741.1
10	0.05	85	2659.8
11	0.03	saturation	101

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Table 3: The enthalpies of condensate from point 13-17

Point	Enthalpy (kJ/Kg)
13	317.7
14	697.1
15	884.6
16	1065.2
17	1287.7

Table 4: The results of the calculated mass flow rate of the bled steam.

Feed heater	Pressure (bar)	Enthalpy h_f (kJ/kg)	Bled Steam	Mass flow rate of bled steam kg/s
1	80	1317.1	y_1	0.1
2	40	1087.4	y_2	0.065
3	20	908.6	y_3	0.029
4	8	720.9	y_4	0.097
5	0.5	340.6	y_5	0.032

Fig. 1: Composition of waste generated in Lagos State

Fig. 2: Schematic layout of the incineration plant

- KEYS**
- Combustion air
 - Condensate
 - Steam
 - Ash
 - Flue gas

Fig. 3: The thermodynamic Cycle Path of the plant

